

Implementation of Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) at the University level

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Abstract

Recently Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) has become well established in the educational system of Kazakhstan. CLIL means teaching a subject, in our case economics and business, through the second language, the Kazakh language at Nazarbayev University. The paper examines the effectiveness of this approach, and provides guidelines for the successful implementation of CLIL. One of the main advantages of this approach is content-driven; the dual focus of teaching both the subject and the language together will increase students' motivation to learn the target language. Learning the language becomes more focused, as the language is used to solve specific communicative tasks. Thus, the ability to communicate in the Kazakh language in a professional context becomes, after all, a priority. This article explores the language of economics and business based on the subject and language materials in the Kazakh language. The author provides suggestions for designing economics- and business-related tasks that both support and develop this language in the classroom. The article concludes with a discussion of the implications of the CLIL approach as it relates to the education of language teachers, their professional challenges, and the development of curriculum materials for students who study economics and business language in Kazakh.

Keywords: Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL); content-driven approach; the Kazakh language

1. Introduction

The globalization process is characterized by increased demand for language education. This is particularly important for Kazakhstan as global integration processes require the formation of a sustainable communication medium as it relates to managing state affairs. Therefore, the issues of language training for the people of Kazakhstan are amongst the most important and urgent tasks facing the national education system.

Kazakhstan has been a bilingual country for more than 70 years. As one of the Republics of the former USSR, the education system is carried out in two languages, Kazakh and Russian. Unfortunately, most of the education was carried out in Russian, thus creating an unbalanced linguistic landscape in the country. Language education and the linguistic landscape of the country has changed only after Kazakhstan declared independence. Maintaining the integrity of the Kazakh language has become essential to restoring the national and cultural identity of the people. Often, schooling for Kazakhs was unavailable in their own language, especially in urban areas where 'such schools were often nearly non-existent' (Olcott, 1985). After gaining independence, it was a major task of Kazakhstan's Government to transform the country into a market economy and to bring the country in line with the globalized world. By "Law on Languages" in Kazakhstan, the Kazakh language is announced as the state language; Russian effectively becomes a lingua franca and English becomes the means of international communication of business. In his annual message in 2007, President Nursultan Nazarbayev emphasized that the younger generation of Kazakhstan must speak three languages: Kazakh, Russian and English in order to become competitive in a globalized world (Nazarbayev, 2007). During the Soviet regime the English language, what was in an expanding circle by Kachru (1992) did not pose an official status and was taught as one of the foreign languages among other European languages, like German and French. Within 20 to 25 years after independence, the expansion of the English language increased dramatically. English became the language of communication between Kazakhstan and international multinational corporations in an effort to attract foreign investment to the country. The next reason for the extension of English was the official joining of Kazakhstan to the Bologna declaration, what caused dramatic changes in the higher education system of Kazakhstan. As a result, the teaching of languages, including Kazakh, required all materials and the teaching methodologies to be brought up to the current standards. The updating of language education in the Republic of Kazakhstan implies the implementation of a policy of trilingual education by creating the necessary conditions for organizing the educational process in Kazakh, Russian and English. Especially, the teaching of the Kazakh language as an F2 (foreign language) drew the attention of language learners, teachers, scientists and parents alike. The lack of appropriate methodical supplements, published books, and modern methodology was apparent. In this regard, CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) is an innovative learning approach that involves teaching different courses (Content Learning) through an L2 (Language Learning). CLIL started to be implemented in the teaching process of the Kazakh language as an L2 at secondary and high educational institutions.

The main purpose of this article is to study such an educational approach as an integrated content-language learning, which is considered by the author as an effective tool for the formation of content competency in L2, in our case, the Kazakh language, in high education. In this respect, the question arises for many teachers: "How to build such integrated learning, in which the content component will be preserved, and the students' language competence will improve?" This is the main challenge for CLIL, in our case, for the Kazakh language in English speaking environment at NU.

1.1 The Kazakhstani experience in CLIL

The popularity of CLIL methods in western and in Russian resources, the features of their use at all levels of education are described in detail in numerous studies and are accompanied by positive reviews. In Kazakhstan, the described approach is not substantial, but it implemented in fragments. Experience in the use of CLIL can be found in the works (Khairullina, 2016; Kakenov, 2017; Karimsakova et.al, 2018) which declare the effectiveness of this technique in secondary and higher education. Accordingly, CLIL methodology is becoming well established in the educational system of Kazakhstan.

In Kazakhstan, the integration of language and subject/content learning began because of Kazakh/Russian bilingualism and then was based on the Kazakh/Russian/English multilingualism. The Russian-Kazakh and vice versa bilingualism has been a historical duet for centuries, and today the national language and the Russian language as a lingua franca, the language of interethnic communication functions in a harmonious combination. Education in the context of bilingualism is recognized by many scientists as one of the opportunities of the most effective organizing teaching a foreign language at school and therefore is in the center of researchers' attention now. Along with culturally focused models assuming development by students the lingual, cross-cultural, social and cultural knowledge subject-oriented models get the relevance in which Russian acts as means of studying subject (mathematics, biology, physics, etc.) (Suleimenova, 2001). In 50's of the last century, most of the Kazakh-speaking population lived in rural areas of the country, so the percentage of Kazakh-schooling was higher than in urban areas. Moreover, financing for Russian and Kazakh schools was not equal. As a result, the level of education provided at Kazakh schools dropped dramatically, as did enrolment: in 1958, 75% of Kazakh children attended Kazakh schools; by 1991, only 34.4% did, most of them being in rural areas (UNDP, 1995). Since Russian became the dominant language in society and knowledge of the language offered higher economic and educational returns. The language of instruction at former educational bodies, such as universities, and other institutions in Kazakh Soviet Socialist Republic, especially at technical institutions was Russian. At the university level, Kazakh as a language of instruction was used only in humanities and agricultural departments (Smagulova, 2006). Therefore, the graduates from rural high schools had to study at universities, where all curricula from the beginning were in the Russian language. For students, who graduated from Kazakh schools, there was no language support to overcome linguistic difficulties. Students had to overcome all language related issues by themselves. As a result, the students' assessments were affected and resulted in the low literacy levels of the non-Russian citizens of the country.

In language teaching methodology subject/content-language training does not have a long history. Until the end of the 90's special courses, such as "Methods of teaching Kazakh languages to non-Kazakhs" was being developed. In teaching a foreign language, it was called "Methods of teaching foreign languages to non-linguists". The training was more theoretical and focused on reading and translation. The needs of society were limited with the written communication, and due to the political situation, oral communication was not in high demand. Since the 1950's English-speaking specialists were trained in the Kazakh State University of International Relations and World Languages named after Abylai Khan for English and in other higher and secondary schools. English was included in the school program as a separate subject. The results of these initiatives were CLIL educational materials - English for lawyers, physicists, mathematicians, biologists, etc., however, most of them were in Russian as the main language of instruction and communication. This approach was implemented as an effective attempt to conduct language teaching, especially for the methodology of teaching different content subjects through the Russian language for many years. Due to the globalization of the education and due to the evolution of knowledge we recognized that this type of education was English for specific purposes (ESP), where the goal of learning is still the language but not the subject. In the last two decades, higher education in Kazakhstan has undergone a period of remarkable change and growth. Education has become one of the urgent needs of the Kazakhstani people, and the integration of a foreign language into educational programs that will ultimately provide Kazakhstani students and scientists the opportunity to represent their country to the world community adequately. There are 42 universities, which have special groups, where English is used as the medium of instruction (EMI) (Seitzhanova et.al, 2015). The opening of the British Council office in Almaty in 1992 was an important event in establishing not only of political but also economic relationship and for strengthening the ties in the sphere of education, especially in English teaching methodology.

The concept of CLIL as a scientific term was introduced in 1994 by D. Marsh, a researcher in the field of multilingual education (Marsh, 2002) and emerged because of the influence of bilingualism ideas. CLIL is promoted as a distinct pedagogical practice in second language acquisition, distinct from bilingual education, content-based instruction and immersion (Coyle, 2007). In the Kazakhstani educational system, the CLIL approach in the framework of the educational process is practiced very rarely. Undoubtedly, the development of language competence in schools and universities of Kazakhstan could move to a qualitatively new level, if this approach were to be carefully studied, and the mechanisms for its implementation in the learning process were mastered. CLIL was originally used in secondary schools, which turned out to be "as a suitable option in this dilemma in how to educate bilingual students because it is a dual-focused educational approach in which an additional language is used for the learning and teaching of both content and language" (Coyle et.al, 2010).

In Kazakhstani practice of secondary schools used to utilize team teaching, the cooperation of content and foreign language teachers working together. In those CLIL classes, the content teachers delivered the topic with the second language teacher's support, whose role was narrowed down just too unnecessary translation. Moreover, this working together a pair of two teachers in one class was one of the major drawbacks in CLIL (also, Banegas, 2014; Cammarat & Tedick, 2012, p. 251-269; Coonan, 2007; Coyle, 2007; Coyle, Hood, & Marsh, 2010, p. 44; Mehisto et al., 2014).

Currently, CLIL is implemented in three models:

- learning the language separately and in advance, as preparation for the study of the subject in the language;
- learning a foreign language through subject content that has already been learned in their native language;
- study of language and subject within one course (Lucietto, 2008). The latter model is more in line with the CLIL scripts.

This model of learning the language and the subject within one course corresponds to the practice of language teaching in our university; however, it is adjusted in the line with the needs of the students and the organization of the educational process at Nazarbaev University.

In various ways, the pedagogical communities of Russia and the countries of Europe concluded that CLIL is the most effective known remedy for the "treatment of language crisis" that has arisen in society in general and in higher education (Sidorenko & Rybushkina, 2017). It is true that the competence of the English language is in great demand in a globalized world. That is why English is the target language in current CLIL classes around the world. "Despite implementation differences in the international scene when responding to CLIL, a common goal will also be found to apply throughout the different contexts: most countries try to find a coherent answer to the need for language competence and communication in this globalized world, with the knowledge of languages as a key factor for job opportunities and promotion" (Ruiz de Zarobe, 2013). However, effective participation in a globalized world requires not only competence in English; but also depends on the language course of each country. "Legal regulation of the functional status of the Kazakh language was a logical start to improve the language situation in Kazakhstan. The main change in the status of the official, the Kazakh language is a clear definition of the conditions for the implementation of the language of the main nationality that was previously the privilege of the Russian language" (Beisenova, 2013).

1.3 Implementation CLIL at Nazarbayev University and its program goals

In the current days, a linguistic repertoire of youth is manifested in the consolidation of learning other languages in addition to Kazakh and local ethnic languages. For this reason, Kazakhstan's language management aims to maximize the internationalization and revitalization of participant languages in the language context of the country. The linguistic repertoire of young people is a necessary aspect of not only individual identification, but also one of the pressing factors for the further development of the country's language policy. The elevating of the status of the state language and expanding its usage in all social structures and government systems is the highest priority of Kazakhstani language policy. The Republic of Kazakhstan requires proficiency in Kazakh for government employment and recently the President asked that parliament and the government conduct business in Kazakh. NU graduates should be able to function at that level. At the same time, there is a risk to NU as an institution if it has the reputation of producing graduates who are unable to speak Kazakh.

Students who have grown up in the Republic of Kazakhstan have studied the Kazakh language in grades 1-11, whether it has been in a “Russian language school” or a “Kazakh language school”. Therefore, the competence of students in the state language is one of the main points of the strategic plan of the Nazarbayev University (NU), which is a newly established a world-class university, where English is the medium of instruction. This autonomous educational organization is a unique American-based model institution, intended to set forth new policies governing the Kazakh Language curriculum at NU. NU, with its academic freedom and autonomy, conducts integrated learning with regard to the National Program "Language Trinity" (Kazakh, Russian and English or other foreign languages). From the first years of its operation, a special department of the Kazakh language was organized. It was a great support to the development of the state language and a noteworthy contribution to the project "State Program for the Functioning and Development of Languages for 2011-2020". The current Department of Kazakh and Turkic studies (renamed in 2017) in the School of Sciences and Humanities (SSH) offers a flexible curriculum that is designed to meet the needs of the different groups of students, so that all NU graduates develop a deep knowledge of Kazakh language, literature and culture, and are effective communicators in the state language in professional settings.

Let us consider some features of teaching the Kazakh language in NU, which, in our opinion, should be considered when working and developing CLIL methods: Nazarbayev University supports social and cultural programs for the implementation of the Kazakh language policy of the country. Some studies emphasize the multifunctional use of the Russian language in the daily life of Kazakhstan. Some researchers state that the university language education is not able to adequately respond to the urgent need of the Kazakhstan labor market for staff with a high level of bilingual vocational language training. On the contrary, it contributes to the preservation and reproduction of the Russian language as the preferred language of communication in the professional and business sphere (Akzhigitova & Zharkynbekova, 2013). Even though Kazakhstan has been an independent country for more than 29 years, the Kazakhstani language situation is defined as the mostly bilingual with the predominance of the Russian language in business, media, and press. To date, the lack of personnel of the new generation, able to deeply understand the issues of modern economics and policies in the sphere of public service of the Republic of Kazakhstan, in our opinion, is connected with the psychological factors of successful study of not only foreign, as well as a state language in the learning process. Namely, this problem is typical for civil servants who are making efforts to continue their education in the language vertically, and they begin to study the state language in adulthood. Acting as subjects of public service activities, they are the ones who intend to be able to understand complex economic and political issues. Therefore, in the context of the socio-economic crisis, the Republic of Kazakhstan needs to train competent personnel in the management of public services, personnel whose Kazakh language competency is adequate to implement such strategic tasks. Based on the above, the issues of Kazakh language training of citizens appear today more than ever before among the most important and urgent tasks facing national education, because they are directly related to the solid development of the state and the role of the Kazakh language as the unifying factor of all people of Kazakhstan.

Why we need CLIL? The definition of CLIL also includes reference to an additional language as a medium of instruction, as exemplified in the quote from Coyle. ‘Additional’ language was defined by Marsh (2002) as any language other than the first language, including foreign language, L2, or minority language (Jasone Cenoz et al., 2014). As an innovative approach to teaching and learning foreign languages, CLIL has been widely used as an approach for multilingual education and considered as one of the successful approaches in European contexts (Henn-Reinke, 2012). However, as stated by Coyle (2007), “there is no single blueprint that can be applied in the same way in different countries”. CLIL is an educational approach that is adapted to suit educational policies, which aim to develop specific languages, therefore, in the framework of Kazakhstani trilingual education the term additional and specific language refers to the Kazakh language in NU context. The level of knowledge of the Kazakh language among high school graduates is not always satisfied; it needs to be developed and maintained with modern teaching methods and techniques.

How is CLIL implemented at NU? According to Massler, Stolz, and Queisser (2014) who differentiate two types of CLIL: type A CLIL in subject lessons and type B CLIL language lessons we divide the Kazakh courses regarding the student’s need and course objectives into two groups: classes with soft CLIL and classes with the hard CLIL. In soft CLIL, some language learning is taught with the content, while in hard CLIL the content and language, both taught at the same time. In soft CLIL, we provide language classes based on thematic units with emphasis on content where the syllabus and lesson plans involve a topic-based approach including specific themes or content to be dealt with in the language lesson. In addition to this, the department of Kazakh Language and Turkic Studies plans to introduce a certificate program in professional Kazakh (i.e., Kazakh for a number of specializations such as natural science, biological science/medicine, social science, humanities, etc.). These subjects are thematically based, have some academic content and are Kazakh-medium instructed.

In the section “An Example of a Lesson of a National Currency of Kazakhstan in Kazakh Business (KB) class,” I would like to provide an example of soft CLIL lesson in KB.

1.4 The teacher challenges in CLIL

CLIL is an approach, which integrates the teaching of content from a curriculum subject with the teaching of a non-native language. Teaching any content for F2 students is a difficult but challenging task due to several factors, mainly, satisfying the student’s language needs, institutional academic policy, and teachers experience and readiness to satisfy student’s demands. The CLIL classroom is highly student-focused, the curricular subject and new language skills are taught together. This requires skills and competences of teachers using the CLIL approach (Bertaux et al., 2010; Marsh et al., 2010). These cover e.g., foreign language acquisition by non-language teachers, becoming acquainted with a certain non-language subject (language teachers), the role of teamwork during lessons, CLIL methodology, the way of assessment, how to provide feedback, dealing with multicultural groups, didactics in a multinational group, etc.

So, what language do CLIL teachers teach? It can be described in three categories.

- First, CLIL students need to know content-specific vocabulary for the topic they are learning, in our case, market, unemployment, trade, money, stock exchange, etc., for business. They also learn the grammar which is needed for the subject, such as the past simple tense and ‘used to’ for international trade history, or ‘if...., then ...’ or ‘as ... as’, ‘... than’ sentences for determining fluctuations of national currency.
- CLIL students also need to learn the language to carry out activities during the lesson, such as sentence starters like ‘there is’ or ‘there are’ and sequence markers like ‘firstly’, ‘after that’ or ‘finally’ for writing, or functional language such as ‘I disagree with’ or ‘Shall we decide on’ for group work.
- CLIL students learn the sort of language which helps them organize their thoughts and solve problems, like ‘analyze’, ‘categorize’ or ‘design’.

To determine if teachers of the Kazakh language use this approach, their readiness and their preparation in applying CLIL methodology in class, in this section I would like to describe and justify the choice of methods employed to collect the data. The purpose was to explore the attitudes and challenges of teachers about their teaching experiences in CLIL classes. I decided to apply both quantitative and qualitative data collection tools, most of them chose questionnaires and interviews; for example, Tsuchiya & Pérez Murillo (2015), Dalton-Puffer, Hüttner, Schindelegger & Smit (2009), Yamano (2013), Massler (2012), Ikeda (2013), Wegner (2012), Huang, (2015). Therefore, I employed two data collection tools: paper-based questionnaire and one-on-one, face-to-face interviews. The questionnaire was chosen to gather data from a larger number of teachers from other local Universities. In order to build a broader picture of the issue, and interviews

with my colleagues who teach the Kazakh for Business course along with me in KL&T department to explore it more deeply. The survey consisted of these open-ended questions:

1. Are you familiar with the CLIL methodology?
2. How do you feel about working with CLIL?
3. How effective is CLIL to apply in language teaching?
4. What kind of difficulties/challenges do you face in working with CLIL?
5. Do you want to have a degree in a particular subject (e.g., economics) and at the same time a degree in a second language?
6. Will you develop or deepen your knowledge of the other subject?
7. Have you used the option of the so-called team teaching, i.e., a language teacher cooperates with a subject teacher?

About seventy Kazakh language teachers from different regions of Kazakhstan participated in the survey. They were invited to a seminar series on Computer based language teaching, which is organized by the International Association of the Kazakh language teachers (IATKL). The participants answered the open-ended questions in their own words. These types of questions were useful in eliciting respondent feelings, and to providing some deeper view into the issues.

Table 1: Questions with the analysis of the answers

1	Are you familiar with the CLIL methodology?	25 teachers claimed that they are not familiar with this approach; it is the 36% of all participants.
2	How do you feel about working with CLIL?	The 45 teachers, who are familiar with CLIL, among them (32 teachers) often implement it in a different content area, especially in profession-oriented themes, along with grammar material in the classroom, others say they rarely use it. 25 teachers state that it increases F2 students' achievements in learning both a new language and a new subject at the same time.
3	What kind of difficulties/challenges do you face in working with CLIL?	45 teachers shared in open questions what kind of difficulties/challenges they have: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • lack of appropriate materials in Kazakh, a high level of time consumption for material preparation; • shortage of specialized new technology programs in teaching Kazakh, • low access to Internet in some places, • not good knowledge in content in particular subjects, • not always support from the administration; • Training courses are not available on a regular basis for Kazakh language teachers.
4	Do you want to have a degree in a particular subject (e.g., economics) and at the same time a degree in a second language? Will you develop or deepen your knowledge from the other subject?	38 teachers expressed that there is no need to receiving another degree. They suggested that one could use CLIL, not as a whole subject area, but as a single lesson for your language class. That will still make for a pretty interesting and immersive lesson. Just five of them suggested that they want to deepen their knowledge in economics, and in business, one in Art.
5	Have you used the option of the so-called team teaching, i.e., a language teacher cooperates with a subject teacher?	Some of them used to integrate with history, in geography, but they claimed that team teaching is not always a comfortable way in CLIL.

The second type of survey was a face-to-face interview with my colleagues who teach the Kazakh for business course at NU. The focus group consists of four Kazakh tutors; the interview was conducted at different times, and in different places: in office, in study rooms. The interview produced more information: how to use CLIL in certain topics, what textbooks, video materials, what content do they use etc. This survey was more beneficial in terms of the teaching methodology; it looked like a sharing experience, which was an effective communication for the developing of the Kazakh curricula in CLIL for the future in our department.

I learnt a great deal of information from the conducted surveys. In this regard, there is a big need in developing special CLIL programme in teaching the Kazakh language. Teachers are facing many issues, such as, a lack of preparedness to teach the subject through the CLIL methodology in the Kazakh language, especially in creating the authentic materials adapted to the need of students. From the survey, I can conclude, that CLIL offers a promising path towards reaching the Kazakh language-teaching objective, which has been tested in many areas of education in Kazakhstan, including the secondary level. CLIL approach can be successfully implemented as an effective tool in fulfilling the Kazakh language policy at university level.

1.5 An Example of a Lesson in Kazakh for Business class

CLIL models and pedagogies are initially based on the very same principles, as are communicative language teaching and task-based learning. The difference is that contents/topics acquire a more prominent role, particularly in content-driven CLIL such as bilingual education. In this sense, teacher educators may opt for either developing a CLIL module or deepening the bridges between theory and practice through their own practices. The challenge the former poses is that in order to lead a CLIL module, teacher educators themselves need to be qualified to teach CLIL at higher education level (Banegas, 2012). Armed with this, I would like to give a sample CLIL class, which is introduced at the Nazarbayev University (NU). Usually, the class consists of approximately 18- 20 students. Overall, students at Nazarbayev University come from diverse language backgrounds:

1. Domestic students from primary and secondary schools in which Kazakh was the primary language and instruction
2. Domestic students from primary and secondary schools in which Russian, Uyghur, Uzbek, Kyrgyz, English and other languages were the primary language of instruction
3. International students with varying experiences with Kazakh (with some students having some exposure to the language at home, but no formal instruction or literacy skills, and other students whose Kazakh is at an advanced level).
4. International students with no prior exposure to Kazakh.

In Kazakh, language classes usually sit b, c, and rarely d category students from B2 and C1 levels, which match to the Common European Framework criteria of Reference for Languages. Their Kazakh ability level is defined by the NU's Kazakh language proficiency test (KLPT), which allows students to choose the courses offered by the Kazakh language and Turkic language department. Below I would like to share soft CLIL lesson. The main emphasis of this example lesson is on group work to enable students to acquire teamwork skills and to possess of the subject content of the speech using subject vocabulary, business phrases, and their equivalents in Kazakh.

The didactic potential of CLIL was justified by the British professor D. Coyle in the theory of four "C" - content, communication, cognitive, culture (in English terminology "4 C") (Lucietto, 2008). According to the theory of the English scholar, a symbiosis of linguistic, cultural and social aspects in one approach provides an increase in the general level of language competence, a deeper understanding of the subject content and the development of high-order thinking skills. How I organize the four C-s in this lesson. Content stands for the concept of a National Currency of Kazakhstan in business topic, which is the theme of the soft CLIL lesson. When planning the content of the lessons, it is important to think about the knowledge, skills and understanding that teachers want students to learn, and not just the knowledge they need to acquire. I encourage my students to concentrate the text's content, which provides a wide range of study of the subject, a special terminological base through a Kazakh language and preparation for further professional activities. In order to enrich the student's vocabulary, I urge them to reflect on new words in the text, give a different meaning, and give synonyms, antonyms. After working on new words in the text, I ask them to create some phrases, and then sentences with these words. In the next step, I encourage students engage in meaningful interaction with each other in pair or group works. The goal is for students to create an authentic language, not memorize the rules of grammar and repeat the teacher. I try to group them in a pair, sometime to a group work to communicate to a deeper learning of an F2 and the ability to use acquired competences for applied purposes. In order to increase of the motivational component of students, the development and use of various educational strategies, forms and types of educational activities, to think outside of the box, increase the student's interest to the lesson. In order to motivate them I believe the project work is the best technique, which requires teacher's as well student's creativeness and offers plenty of opportunities to express themselves. As an example, I would like to share my practice working on a project work on topic "How much need Santa Claus and Father Frost money to buy a house in Almaty?" Simulation of different project works is one of the most effective ways to consolidate theoretical knowledge in practice. From this point of view, group or pair work gives good results. It teaches interaction, the ability to allocate roles, adapt to partners, study and research in-group some issues, i.e., forms communicative skills. As communication refers to students using the target language to communicate their thoughts, opinions, attitudes, and discoveries related to the lesson content. Both speaking and writing are emphasized as students "learn to use language and use language to learn" (Coyle, 2007). In the same time different project work develop student's the critical thinking skills that students use to engage and understand course content, to solve problems, and to reflect on their learning, it refers to third C- cognition. During the work on different projects, students learn more broadly local and global cultures. They study, compare and investigate the differences, features, and uniqueness of their own culture and other cultures. Below in the table the stages of the 4 C-s of a project work on a topic "How much money need Santa Claus and Father Frost to buy a house in Almaty?" is given in Table 2:

Table 2: Four C-s and their implementation

Four C-s	How it is implemented?
Content	Reading the text "Tenge is a national currency of Kazakhstan", working on new words, creating phrases, collocations, and then sentences with these words.
communication	A project work on the topic "How much money need Santa Claus and Father Frost to buy a house in Almaty?" The teacher discusses the key steps of the action, the expected results and determines the deadline, divides into groups. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Then each group will share their thoughts, opinions, attitudes; • they incorporate the target-language vocabulary, subject related terms; • they communicate effectively with group members and share their findings about the 'tenge', 'tenge rate', 'real estate price' through a visual and a verbal presentation.
cognition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students analyze the real estate market, how to buy a house for Santa Claus and Father Frost in Almaty city; • compare the house price with other cities, countries; • they evaluate the world economic situation; • they generate and implement a solution and create an infographic presentation.
culture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students get familiar with the history of the national currency; • they will study how the currency relates to the history and culture; • They will learn the effects of globalization in the example of national currency in terms of economic value and cultural interest.

2. Conclusion

In conclusion, in the Kazakhstan education system, CLIL use is fragmentary in the educational process. Undoubtedly, the development of language competence in schools and universities of the Republic Kazakhstan could move to a qualitatively new level in country's multilingual policy, if this approach was thoroughly studied, and the mechanisms of its introduction into the learning process would be mastered. As an umbrella term in the Kazakhstan context, this approach is mainly combined with other approaches, such as LSP, CBI, TBL, and immersion, in which students are offered a certain form of special and academic support in order to facilitate their learning of content through the CLIL methodology in the target language, which is the official state language of Kazakhstan. We consider CLIL will be one of the appropriate approaches in teaching Kazakh as F2 and CLIL performed at NU in the teaching subject content through F2 mainly to non-lingual peer groups. CLIL as a teaching method at university level has its advantages but it also has some drawbacks:

- The implementation of the CLIL at NU increases students' employability in multi-educational society, offers them better job prospects on the labour market (socio-economic objectives);
- To convey to students' values of tolerance and respect vis-à-vis other cultures, through use of the CLIL target language, because they are directly related to the solid development of the state and the role of the Kazakh language as the unifying factor of all Kazakhstani people (socio-cultural objectives);
- Students acquire communicative skills and patterns (Metodický portál, 2013).
- learning enhances critical thinking of students;
- the learning process is based on real life situations and authentic materials;
- leaning is based on teamwork, group work;

In implementation of CLIL, we find out some disadvantages:

- Lack of appropriate materials in Kazakh, a high level of time consumption for material preparation;
- Shortage of specialized new technology programs in teaching Kazakh;
- Low access to Internet, interferences to the quality of the objectives;
- Not enough skilled of teacher's knowledge in particular subjects; this is key!!!!
- Not enough information on the CLIL method in teaching Kazakh; does not matter – it is not language specific
- The administration is not always supportive; the teacher should have appropriate teaching materials and be skilled in using new technology to achieve his goals.
- Training courses are not available on a regular basis for Kazakh language teachers. Recently appeared some online Órleu courses, and some fragments of CLIL classes on YouTube.

If we talk about the national characteristics of the country, which determine the special conditions for the implementation of the CLIL approach at the university level:

1. Kazakhstan is far from large migration processes, it is in the field of interaction of the EAEU, where more the Russian language is a means of interstate communication in the Eurasian region. The majority of the population here speaks Russian, migration is mainly carried out between Russia and Kazakhstan and the former CIS countries.
2. The second reason that should be taken into account when designing CLIL courses is a political and economic reason, which is the lack of willingness of Kazakhstani universities to accept foreign specialists who could provide the proper quality of conducting special subjects in a foreign language, thereby creating a natural communication medium. Kazakhstan's resources are still insufficient, although the educational process in several universities is conducted in English, for example, KBTU, KIMEP, Nazarbayev University, IAB, IT University.
3. Many researchers call CLIL in different ways, methods, approaches, training, teaching methods. There is no consensus, in fact, as elsewhere.

To sum up, CLIL is essential in Kazakhstan to increase the role of the Kazakh language. CLIL should help the Kazakh language as a technique not only for language purposes but also to become a vehicle to teach and learn non-language content. Besides, the CLIL approach is the proper tool in realizing this ambitious aim.

References

- Akzhigitova, A. Sh. & Zharkynbekova, K. (2013). Social aspects of the functioning of the Russian language in the framework of the language policy of the Republic of Kazakhstan: (for example, city Astana). *Sociological research*, 9, 96-99. An introduction to CLIL Notes based on a CLIL course at British Study Center. (2012) Oxford. doi: http://www.itis.biella.it/europa/pdf-europa/CLIL_Report.pdf.
- Banegas, D. L. (2012). CLIL teacher development: Challenges and experiences. *Latin American Journal of Content & Language Integrated Learning*, 5(1), 46-56.
- Banegas, D. (2014). Integrating content and language in English language teaching in secondary education: Models, benefits and challenges. *Studies in Second Language Learning and Teaching*, 2(1), 111-136.
- Beisenova, Z. S. (2013). Language Shifts in Case of Language Policy of Kazakhstan. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies MCSEER Publishing, Rome-Italy*, 2(8), 653-659.
- Bertaux, P., Coonan, C. V., Frigols-Martín, M. J., & Mehisto, P. (2010). *The CLIL teacher's competences grid*. doi: http://tplusm.net/CLIL_Competerences_Grid_31.12.09.pdf.
- Cammarata, L. & Tedick, D. J. (2012). Balancing content and language in instruction: The experience of immersion teachers. *The Modern Language Journal*, 96, 251-269.
- Coonan, M. (2007). Insider views of the CLIL class through teacher self-observation-introspection. *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*, 10(5), 625-646.
- Coyle, D. (2007). Content and language integrated learning: Towards a connected research agenda for CLIL pedagogies. *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*, 10(5), 543- 562.
- Coyle, D., Hood, P., & Marsh, D. (2010). *CLIL: Content and language integrated learning*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Henn-Reinke, K. (2012). *Considering Trilingual Education*. New York: Routledge
- Jasone Cenoz, Fred Genesee, & Durk Gorter. (2014). Critical Analysis of CLIL: Taking Stock and Looking Forward. *Applied Linguistics*, 35(3), 243-262. Kazakhstan joined the Bologna Process. doi: <https://iqaa.kz/en/news/item/1333-kazakhstan-joined-the-bologna-process>.
- Kachru, B. (1992). A Biographical Sketch. *World Englishes*, 11(2-3). 91-94.
- Kakenov, R. (2017). Teachers' experiences of using CLIL in Kazakh language classrooms. *NUGSE Research in Education*, 2(2), 21-29.
- Karimsakova, A.S., Yermenova, K.K., Kuzembayeva, G.A. (2018). CLIL implementation in West Kazakhstan Marat Ospanov state medical university: challenges and experience. *The West Kazakhstan medicine journal*, 57(1), 63-67.
- Khairullina G. D. (2016). Content and language integration in CLIL classes. *Journal of achievements of science and education*, 65-70.
- Lucietto, S. A. (2008). Model for Quality CLIL Provision. *International CLIL Research Journal*, 1(1), 83-92.
- Marsh, D. (Ed.). (2002). *CLIL/EMILE: The European dimension*. Jyväskylä, Finland: University of Jyväskylä.
- Marsh, D., Mehisto, P., Wolff, D., & Frigols-Martin, M. (2010). *The European Framework for CLIL Teacher Education*. Graz: European Centre for Modern Languages (ECML).

- Marsh, D. (2012). *Content and language integrated learning (CLIL): A Development trajectory*. Servicio de Publicaciones de la Universidad de Córdoba, Spain.
- Massler, U., Stotz, D., & Queisser, C. (2014) Assessment instruments for primary CLIL: the conceptualisation and evaluation of test tasks. *The Language Learning Journal*, 42(2), 137-150.
- Mehisto, P., Kambatyrova, A., & Nurseitova, A. (2014). Three in one? Trilingualism in educational policy and practice. In D. Bridges (Ed.), *Educational reform and internationalization: The case of school reform in Kazakhstan* (pp. 152-176). Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Nazarbayev, N. (2007). Address of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan to the People of Kazakhstan. doi:http://www.akorda.kz/en/addresses/addresses_of_president/address-of-the-president-of-the-republic-of-kazakhstan-nursultan-nazarbayev-to-the-people-of-kazakhstan-february-28-2007
- Olcott, M. B. (1985). *The politics of language reforms in Kazakhstan, in Sociolinguistic Perspectives on Soviet National Languages: Their Past, Present and Future*, ed. I. Kreindler, Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter, 183 – 204.
- Ruiz de, Z. (2013). CLIL implementation: From policy-makers to individual initiatives. *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*, 16(3), 231-243.
- Seitzhanova, A., Plokhikh, R., Baiburiev R., & Tsaregorodtseva A. (2015). English as the medium of instruction: Modern tendency of education in Kazakhstan. *PRADEC Conference Proceedings*, 3(1), 74-77.
- Sidorenko, T.V., & Rybushkina, S.V. (2017). Integrated subject-language training and its prospects in Russian technical Universities. *The Education and Science Journal*. 19(6), 182-193.
- Smagulova, J. (2006). Kazakhstan. Language, identity and conflict. *Journal Innovation: The European Journal of Social Science Research*, 19(3, 4), 303-320.
- Suleimenova, E. D. (2001) Bulletin of Al-Farabi Kazakh National University (series: philological), *Almaty*, 16, 19–30. The CLIL Guidebook. doi: <https://www.languages.dk/archive/clil4u/book/CLIL%20Book%20En.pdf>
- The Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan (2010). *State Program of Education Development in the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2011-2020*. doi: <https://kaznmu.kz/eng/state-program-of-education-development-in-the-republic-of-kazakhstan/>
- UNDP. Kazakhstan: Human Development Report. (1995). doi: <http://hdr.undp.org/en/content/general-human-development-report-kazakhstan-1995>